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Deliverable 3.1

Photonics for experiments – development of the “OmniLight Laboratory”

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this document is to describe progress in the research and development related to Deliverable 3.1 Photonics for experiments – development of the “OmniLight Laboratory” of the H2020 project Photonics4All, realized within the period of months M0-M12 of the project duration.

The concept of the **OmniLight Laboratory** is “promoting light with light”. It is envisioned as a hardware and software tool for light-based scientific shows, with the goal of supporting and maximizing the impact of professional presentations. It should provide a possibility to demonstrate the principles and applications of light, while using the advanced modes of light detection, control and modulation. The ultimate aim of this task is to provide an interactive “light laboratory” for presentation and education of photonics in many related outreach activities (namely training workshops, exhibitions, scientific events).

The OmniLight Laboratory deliverable has two main phases. During the first - **development phase (2015)**, a set of presentation tools focused on photonics and light-based technologies was developed as a concept and a prototype in following keypoints:

- Selection of key technologies and hardware solutions, M0 - M9
- Tender procedures M9 - M11
- Assembly, testing, preliminary use M10 - M11
- OmniLight Laboratory first prototype M12

Exploitation of the prototype and its optimization with respect to different applications will be relevant in the **second phase** of the project (**2016**).

2. Design and Development

2.1 The concept, implementation and main features

A **modular instrumentation** for light-based scientific show was designed, aiming to provide an interactive laboratory for presentation and education of Photonics which is going beyond the state-of-the-art devices and tools currently used for photonics outreach. With this focus in mind, we did extensive overview and testing of different devices and technologies that provide various modes of light detection and modulation. Based on this preparatory work, a conceptual scheme was developed as shown at Fig.1. We decided that the OLL system will be based on a combination of the “classical” projection using data/video projector and the laser-based display (beam scanning) device, with the addition of the advanced real-time sensing capability. We also decided to use leading-edge, but as much as possible industry-

standard solutions in all components, due to future compatibility, replaceability and possible improvement of the developed solution.

Very important decisions were needed to identify common needs of the future users. Based on our own outreach experience, we decided the system be oriented towards small to mid-scale environments, such as seminar rooms, multimedia classrooms, smaller conference halls. Larger venues normally need much brighter light sources which increase both size, weight and price of the components used. Another decision was done concerning the mode of presentation, where we opted for a screen-based projection with a possibility to create tabletop experiments as an option. This primary mode was chosen mostly due to safety concerns using higher-power laser sources, which should not be directed towards audience and the level of back-reflected light should be controlled as well.

Fig.1. Conceptual scheme of OmniLight laboratory.

In case of data/video projection systems, current consumer market provides numerous solutions spanning from XGA (1024x768) up to WUXGA (1920x1200) resolution, with TFT vs. DLP chip technologies providing different quality of color representation. For the intended use, however, resolution was not the only selection

parameter. Very important for variable-space installations is the available luminous power and runtime parameters of the light source. Halogen or mercury-lamp based projection provides reasonable optical power, but the light generation is relatively ineffective and generate excessive heat. Since in our application (densely-packed transportable container) heat management and power consumption were crucial, we opted for a more advanced alternative provided by combined laser/led hybrid light source developed by Casio (<http://www.casioprojector.com/home>). The projection system **XJ-M141** selected for OLL prototype is based on the DLP chip with native resolution of XGA and 2500 ANSI lumen optical output, which is a reasonable compromise between size, price, performance and runtime features of the device.

With respect to laser display device, we successfully utilized the fact that in Bratislava there exist a good local industrial base for laser display manufacturing (<http://www.kvantlasers.sk/2015-ilda-awards>), which allows us to develop customized version of the device and software used in the OLL prototype. We opted for **1.8 W RGB laser display** (<http://www.kvantlasers.sk/products/full-colour-lasers>) with optical bank, which is a DMX-controlled motorized add-on module allowing modifying output from the display by using different optical elements. The software and control is discussed in the next session of this document.

Fig.2. OmniLight laboratory prototype.

The whole OmniLight Laboratory system was assembled into an industry standard rack (see Fig.2) on rolls to be transportable (for events – see dissemination chapter), together with small form-factor computer (HP 400 G2 desktop), 23.5"

touchscreen display, DMX control module and necessary cabling. The main screen with three overlaying optical projections (projector, laser display and optical effects) are shown at Fig. 3. Live performance of the prototype is shown and discussed in more details in the video description, which accompanies this report as a supplement and is available online at Photonics4all project youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vBwM1S1yXV8>.

Fig.3. OmniLight laboratory main screen with overlaid projection, laser graphics and optical effects.

Regarding the real-time optical sensing, we opted for an industry leading solution provided in the form of a **Kinect sensor**. The Kinect is a motion sensing input device developed by Microsoft for Xbox and Windows-based systems. Kinect sensor features an RGB camera, depth sensor and multi-array microphone, which together provide full-body 3D motion capture, facial recognition and voice recognition capabilities. It also provides an SDK library for custom application development, which is crucial for our intended use within the interactive laboratory concept. Within the project realization we successfully used the SDK for customized live performances and real-time parameter control (see example at Fig.4).

In addition to Kinect sensor, which is used for detection/control from the presenter side, we decided to use also one additional **analogue video-camera** with zoom optics, which is aligned in parallel with the projection systems and detects the main screen for real-time optical feedback demonstration. This effect gives a nice demonstration of active optical amplification, resonator modes and pulse generation in a very simple but graphically interesting way (Fig. 5).

Fig.4. Microsoft Kinect sensor interface.

Fig.5. Real-time analogue feedback. Left: videocamera aligned in parallel with the DLP projector, right: silhouette with real-time feedback generated pattern (green).

Some examples of the different modes of presentation are given at Fig.6. The first picture show laser graphics ("P4All" text) multiplied with the optical diffraction grating element, the position/orientation of which can be controlled by the user. Another example is a modified silhouette ("ghost"), projected by laser projector through a non-homogenous glass. The silhouette is a dynamic representation of the 3D data

scanned by Kinect sensor and used by the custom developed software plug-in within Fiesta software bundle driving the laser display.

Fig.6. Different effects of the Optical bank.

As an example of another option / module for the photonics public experiment we also tested a small *fiber optic spectrometer* for real-time colorimetry and spectroscopy purposes in conjunction with programmable LED reflector (Fig. 7).

Fig.7. Colors and spectroscopy. Left: variable-color LED reflector (orange-red circle), right: compact fiber optic spectrometer.

Laser safety

Due to high-power laser available in the OLL prototype, the safety and security issues are to be considered in all planned public events. In regard to specific and complex security and safety standards for the work with lasers in each individual European country, this could be an obstacle in planning of the events. However, the responsible partner (ILC) has solid experience concerning standards and regulations for lasers and will consider them at all steps of the relevant applications in collaboration with the local organizing authorities, in tight collaboration with other members of P4all consortium having specific expert knowledge in this field.

2.2 Software

During the development phase we opted to use industry standard and widely spread software for projection of data and images, such as Microsoft Office, OpenOffice, or Adobe Pdf reader. However, for more advanced computer manipulation of images and other digital content, an open source software *Processing* was selected (<https://www.processing.org>). This flexible java-based environment is very popular among art-related community which open space for further collaborative projects and performances (see example of the output at Fig. 8). In contrast to aforementioned "business" or desktop publishing graphics solutions, *Processing* can access real-time control from various devices, such as Kinect or midi devices. This is very valuable in the case of need for quick reaction during the show, such as the ongoing discussion with audience, with the need to provide answers about particular optical effects etc.

Fig.8. Example of the Processing-based computer graphics with laser overlay.

For laser display projection we opted for a Fiesta software (<http://www.showtacle.com>), which - due to our previous collaboration with its creator - was open for additional custom modules that provides beyond-commercial solutions (such as Kinect-based laser movement / painting, walking silhouettes etc.).

To underline the uniqueness of the developed solution, it is noteworthy to say that the OmniLight laboratory prototype is based on combination of a commercially available software and custom developed instrumentation that is resulting from a previous long-term development and collaboration between Kvant company and members of the project consortium (ILC team) in the field of interactive laser display technology. In particular, we were involved in design and development of the module interfacing the Kinect sensor with the Fiesta software, which is driving the laser scanner. This combination alone (available commercially here: <http://www.kvantlasers.sk/product/interactivelaserman-bundle-a3400>) offers beyond state-of-the-art possibilities in creation of laser performances. In our project we would like to extend this concept even further, as we combine together different display technologies and optical effects + feedback, pushing the limits of the future applications on the new levels of creativity. To our knowledge there exist no other instrumentation with these features available for the field of Photonics / Science outreach.

2.3 Integration and Optimization

OmniLight Laboratory will help to provide leading-edge content for photonics science shows and educational presentations given by the consortium members. After successful development of the first functional prototype (provided in M12) we plan to enter the second phase of development where the feedback from the members of P4All consortium and external users will be gathered and evaluated. Based on this feedback, an upgraded design / development will be realized leading to the assembly of a second version of the prototype to be presented in M24.

In the very initial state (before construction of the first prototype), the hardware and software elements were running more-less independently, and could be used to show experiment or answer public question based on the sole capability of the presenter. As an example, if the spectator asked about color mixing, it was possible to show a white beam which was subsequently divided into individual color beams using the diffractive elements. Another example might be a question about fluorescence, and demonstration that blue-green light is able to excite fluorescein solution while the yellow-red light could not. It is very important to note, however, that all these experiments require a **pre-defined library** of image, text and laser-graphics content to be prepared by a user (e.g. white or color beams of defined intensity and direction in the examples given above). The definition of such library or data-bank suitable for scientific show(s) on Photonics is a subject of currently ongoing work on the system optimization, and will be provided as a final solution in the second version of the OLL prototype.

One of the most important issues of Task 3.1 is to ensure utilization of the developed OLL prototype in other P4all activities and its further optimization. ILC will provide dissemination of the OLL system at major Slovak and selected European science and technology exhibitions (see the following session). In the second phase of P4all project, customization of OmniLight Laboratory is envisioned with respect to other P4All tasks related to public outreach. The intended next step in the integration of the OLL system is to achieve direct interconnection between modules of Photonics APPs and Photonics Explorer based experiments and the OmniLight Laboratory library of experiments. In this respect, we will utilize the modular and scaleable concept of the prototype.

2.4 Exploitation strategy

The primary intended users of the OmniLight laboratory are lecturers and presenters, not individual students. The goal of the prototype is to maximize the impact of their presentations using available means of controlling light. An example of such approach is the interactive science show with Kinect controller, showing the principles of laser and other photonics devices (sensors, etc.). It is suitable to be implemented at different outreach events for the general public and also within many other activities planned in Photonics4all project, such as within WP1 (T1.3 Photonics for videos, T1.5 Photonics for schools), WP2 (Photonics for entrepreneurs) and possibly some other activities. The developed tool will be offered and used by other partners and related institutions in all representing European countries in this project. ILC as a task leader of T3.1 will conduct the dissemination and exploitation of the developed prototype addressing the general public. Hereby ILC will use the OmniLight Laboratory at least **two public events**, such as the 'Night of the researchers' in Slovakia and various scientific festivals.

To provide more details on its possible exploitation, a **Questionnaire** has been developed, which was consulted with the P4all partners at M6 Project meeting and will be further distributed to consortium members of EC projects like P4all, Laserlab Europe, as well as to local partners (namely Universities and companies gathered in Photonics Clusters).

In addition to the statements above, the final strategic aim of OmniLight Laboratory development is to provide a functional prototype for possibly regular product. Preliminary marketing activities should be started in collaboration with the local companies. Therefore, in the upcoming period ILC will start discussion with the company Kvant about possible production and marketing of the final product, as it depends on particular technical solutions and IPR on software/hardware components developed as parts of the final prototype. The company will be asked to present it as a prototype at fairs around Europe and do preliminary marketing for the OLL system.

Existing local partnership with companies, where collaboration is envisioned during the development and dissemination of OLL system:

Conceptual development (Kvant, SiProgs)
Technical development (Kvant, SiProgs)
Distribution and applications (Kvant, Ogmium, Saftra Photonics)
Investors and IPR (Neology, Neology Ventures)

3. Dissemination of the OmniLight Laboratory and its components in 2015

The OmniLight Laboratory was developed to increase the awareness about photonics by the general public, children, teenagers and also possibly entrepreneurs. Based on previous experiences of the ILC in conducting such events, and with the help of other experimental photonics outreach tools, at least 6,000 people were directly reached within the first year of the project with activities related to and/or supported by the P4all Task 3.1 (see details further).

3.1 Photonics for schools

Within its development phase, the components of OmniLight laboratory have been tested and used at several occasions. Science show / lecture „**Photonics - the secret world of Light**“ has been delivered as a part of „Superschool of Bratislava“ with the partnership of GoPhoton! Project and National Centre for Popularization of science and technology in Society in Bratislava. The lecture in all cases took around 1 teaching hour (45min) and has been presented at following places:

Gymnázium Bilikova, Bratislava (sec. school, 17y), ~25people, 1 teacher,

Elementary school Nejedleho, Bratislava (prim. school, 12y), ~25people, 1 teacher,

Elem. school Sokolikova, Bratislava (primary school, 12y), ~ 40 people, 2 teachers,

Elem. school Benovskeho, Bratislava (primary school, 12y), ~ 25 people, 1 teacher.

Fig.9. Lectures at Superschool of Bratislava.

During the aforementioned lectures, basic concepts of the “public experiments” with light and photonics elements has been tested, and most promising ones were selected for further integration. Modified for general public, the science show / lecture „**Photonics - the secret world of Light**“ has also been presented on May 16, 2015 (~60 people, 2 hours) as the event under the framework of the Night of Museums and Galleries (www.nocmuzei.sk/nocmuzeiagalerii/nmg2015/index.php) at the Exploratorium in the Main building of Slovak National Museum.

Fig.10. Lecture at Slovak National Museum.

Science show / lecture „**Lasers – from fiction to reality**“ has been delivered on May 22, 2015 at the Festival of Films on Physics (www.fyzikalnefilmy.sk), for the audience of ~150 people and duration of 1 hour.

Fig.11. Lecture (above) and the separate OLL components (right).

3.2 International Year of Light and Light-based Technologies events.

The **European Researchers' Night** is one of the biggest annual events for Science outreach in Slovakia and Europe. GoPhoton! and Photonics4all project were represented in the joined interactive exhibition provided by ILC in Bratislava through hands-on experiments to promote the "Photonics App" as well as other developed tools of Photonics4all project. Science show / lecture „**Photonics - technology of the future century**” was delivered as a part of the Night of the researchers event on September 25, 2015 with the use of OmniLight laboratory components.

Following the first Saturday in October (3.10.2015) in Košice (attended by 30.000 people) the “**Nuit Blanche**” art festival moved for the first time to capital Bratislava. On Saturday 10.10. 2015, 150 national and international artists presented pieces of art to large cultural community of the capital which were admired by more than 100,000 visitors. During this event and the related **Festival of Light** (individual project supported from Visegrad fund) the team from ILC presented several installations, majority of which were supported by and dedicated to **GoPhoton! Splash** event. Great reception at the festival received the “Resonator” – an interactive laser harp that has woken up the square near Slovak National Theatre and the Eurovea complex (Fig.12). The "Resonator" was an original installation by D. Chorvat from International Laser Center with support of Photonics4all project, utilizing some of the OmniLight laboratory components. The installation was based on the relationship between light and sound, while also demonstrating the principle of laser as a quantum resonator (<http://bielanoc.sk/umelci?c=ba&l=en>).

Due to success of the festival and installations provided by ILC, the same concept was chosen for opening ceremony of the **Week of Science and Technology** in Slovakia, held one month later under the auspices of the Ministry of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic (Fig.13).

Fig.12. The Resonator, installation that was designed and delivered for several events of YoL with the support of GoPhoton! and P4all projects. From left to right: installation in at Nuit Blanche Kosice, Festival of Light Bratislava, Week of Science and Technology Bratislava.

Fig.13. Opening ceremony of the Week of Science and Technology in Bratislava with the presence of J.Draxler, Minister of of Education, Science, Research and Sport of the Slovak Republic.

3.3 Future events

The centre of the dissemination and exploitation strategy for OmniLight laboratory is participation at relevant events, and presentations on fairs with industrial partners. Within the Photonics4All project, partners organize a great range of events that contribute to the dissemination and exploitation of the OLL prototype. The following table gives an overview of the currently planned suitable events, dates and locations:

Event	Location	Date
Long Night of Research	Graz, Austria	2016-04-22
Festival of Light (Festival della Luce)	Como, Italy	2016-05-06 to 2016-05-15
Researcher's Night	Bratislava, Slovakia	2016-09-25
Festival of Light	Bratislava, Slovakia	October 2016
Day of Photonics	Zilina, Slovakia	2016-10-21

Week of Science and Technology	Bratislava, Slovakia	November 2016
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Table 1: Events organized by the Photonics4All partners in 2016, where the OmniLight Laboratory is planned to be presented.

In addition to public performances, all partners of the P4all project could disseminate **original video content** acquired by using OLL at their events like campaigns and children universities to generate more viewers and feedback, as well as potential customers. The ILC team is now developing a system for simple online sharing of the educational content that will serve the purpose of the hub providing the P4all consortium with the multimedial material generated by the previously developed tools and kits.

4. Executive Summary

- ✓ The OmniLight Laboratory **concept** has been developed based on previous experience and scientific shows and presentations delivered by the ILC team during the first year of the project duration.
- ✓ The **prototype** of the OmniLight Laboratory has been developed and documented (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vBwM1S1yXV8>)
- ✓ The prototype and its parts were conceptually **tested** at several **public performances and lectures**.
- ✓ **Dissemination and exploitation strategy** for the prototype has been developed.